

Wakeful-sleep to God-realization: Transforming ordinary consciousness into spiritual consciousness

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Abstract

In the modern scientific age, science and humanity are in the search of ultimate truth. Sustained efforts are made from the both ends, but the considerable success has yet not been witnessed. Science and humanity seek to achieve ultimate truth with their limited knowledge of mind and matter i.e. the ordinary consciousness; state of waking sleep. Ultimate truth is not a matter nor it is a material, it is spirit, pure spirit and nothing but spirit. It can only be realized by entering into higher states of consciousness. Transformation to higher states of consciousness is the path traversed towards ultimate truth- God realization. Sant Mat- Religion of saints describes such path leading to portal of spiritual consciousness and the mansion of supreme spirit.

Keywords: Consciousness, Ordinary Consciousness, Spiritual Consciousness, Ultimate Truth, Transformation

In the present age of science; discoveries and inventions are directed towards harnessing the nature by exploring its hidden secrets and truths. Scientists are in hope and desire of knowing all about the nature; their efforts being hard and sustained, yet not considerable results have been witnessed. The reason behind this is well explained through the words of Sir Sahabji Maharaj that the line pursued by them to attain their goal is not the true line. Truth is not a matter, nor a material substance, to be approached or tackled with material instruments. It is spirit, pure spirit and nothing but spirit. The spirit is the life giving and vitalizing principle in the man and the creator and sustainer of the man. It stands for the consciousness of highest and purest order. The realization of the spirit is the ultimate truth, it is the supreme consciousness. It is impossible for the delicate and powerful instruments, invented by science to attain this ultimate truth. It is due to the fact that science is just restricted to the ordinary limits of mind and matter; referred to as ordinary consciousness. An ordinary consciousness is the knowledge obtained through the senses or through the process of syllogistic reasoning. It is related to the everyday, ordinary awareness of our body, ego and personality. It extends in three states of human consciousness viz. the wakeful state, the dream state and the state of deep sleep. It is merely the awareness of the world around us and is changeable and intermittent in nature. The average, ordinary human being is only partially conscious due to the character of the untrained mind and the influence of 'lower' impulses and preoccupations. As a result, most humans are considered to be asleep (to reality) even as they go about their daily business. This ordinary condition of humanity is often termed as "waking sleep". Ordinary consciousness state is the state of forgetfulness and being unconscious. In this state; man has forgotten his own pre-temporal state in God and sees the world as reality. Ordinary consciousness is thus of very lower level and there is dire need to raise our consciousness to higher levels of consciousness to realize the ultimate truth- God perception. Besides three states of consciousness, there exist the states of higher consciousness; generally regarded as a developed state of consciousness in which aspects of the mind, such as thought, perception and attention, are improved, refined and enhanced. These are considered to be a higher level of consciousness relative to ordinary consciousness, in the sense that a greater awareness of reality is achieved. In a secular context, higher consciousness is usually associated with exceptional control over one's mind and will, intellectual and moral enlightenment, and profound personal growth. In a spiritual context, it may also be associated with transcendence, spiritual enlightenment, and union with the divine- God perception. It refers to the awareness or

knowledge of an 'ultimate reality' which traditional theistic religion has named God. In the words of, Sir Sahabji Maharaj;

“The realization of the spirit is a condition or state of consciousness of the highest and purest order. It is the spiritual consciousness independent of every kind of external stimulus. To attain it, all the activities of physical senses and the mind have to be brought to a stand- still, for; otherwise, it is not possible to shut off the influence of external stimuli. In a word, the road to the ultimate truth lies inwards and not outwards, and man stands in the need of being put on this road and helped and guided till he reaches the goal i.e. realizes the spirit-the ultimate truth”

- Writings and Speeches of Param Guru Huzur Sahabji Maharaj. pp. 3

According to Sir Sahabji Maharaj; so far as spiritual development is concerned, we are like the child. And since our spiritual faculties are undeveloped, we can not observe spiritual phenomenon. Just as the child requires the help of the mother or the teacher for physical and mental development, so also do we require for spiritual development the help of one spiritually developed. Just as the child has to perform physical and mental exercises with the help of mother or the teacher, so we have to perform the spiritual exercises under the guidance of living adept. Search and devotion of the living adept is the prerequisite condition in Sant Mat- Religion of saints.

*“Pichlon ki taj tek, tere bhale ki kahoan;
Waqt guru ko maan, tere bhale ki kahoan”*

- Sarbachan, Bachan 29, Shabda 1

(Give up dependence on the people of past, I speak unto you for your good.
And have faith in the living guru, I speak unto you for your good.)

Spiritual approaches to consciousness involve the idea of altered states of consciousness or spiritual experience. Changes in the state of consciousness can occur spontaneously or as a result of spiritual practices being performed under the guidance of living adept. With such practices being performed; transition takes place from the ordinary conscious state on to the higher states of consciousness, new faculties of higher and purer order that lie dormant, comes into play and experiences of higher and purer order are experienced. As discussed earlier that ultimate truth lies inwards and not outwards, the transformation from the outer world to the inner world is required. Kabir says

“Mūṅḍ līe darvāje, Bājīale anhad bāje”

-Adi Granth, pp. 656

(I have now closed off the doors, and the unstruck celestial sound current resounds)

Different brain centers are energized through these practices and it produces the different states of consciousness. There are the number of areas in the brain which have different duties assigned to them and which, on being energized, produce different states of consciousness and different experiences. In relation to the ordinary states of consciousness; the scientists have succeeded in mapping out some parts of the brain with reference to the functions they perform in regulating different organs of the body and ordinary states of consciousness. This knowledge they possess with regard to the functions of the brain and its different areas, is unfortunately meager. However in addition to the different centers localized by the scientists, saints have described the presence of number of other centers situated in the fissure between the two lobes of the brain. Excitation of one or the other of these centers leads to spiritual awakening and the practitioner obtains the flashes of intuition and peeps into the mysteries of the spiritual planes. In the language of adepts one such centre is known as Dasma-dawara (the tenth door), which if

energized, produces spiritual consciousness and opens the way to the mansion of the supreme spirit. Guru Amardas says

“Nao darvāje dasvai mukṭā anhaḍ sabad vajāvaniā”

-Adi Granth, M 3, pp. 110

(Beyond the nine gates, the Tenth Gate is found, and liberation is obtained. The Unstruck Melody of the Shabad vibrates)

Thus, the seeker of truth, guided and helped by his living adept travels on the road leading from the wakeful state to the dream state to deep sleep and so onto the states of trance, ecstasy etc.; transforming his ordinary consciousness into spiritual consciousness to attain the portal of spiritual consciousness and the mansion of supreme spirit. This is the path of transformation of ordinary consciousness into spiritual consciousness leading to God realization. Sant Mat in this modern era emphasized upon these spiritual practices to awaken our dormant spiritual faculties to attain the ultimate truth- God realization. Spiritual practices were the essential teachings of all religions; unfortunately which are not being nowadays pursued. Sant Mat thus revived the core of all religions and gave the secrets of higher realms of spirituality. As in the words of Prof. P.S. Satsangi Sahib;

“It is only with the advent of Param Purush Puran Dhani Soamiji Maharaj that in the religion of saints the ultimate consciousness or the super consciousness of the highest order has been revealed”

- Discourses on Education in Dayalbagh: A Vision of Complete Education, pp. 254

Striking a balance between spiritualism & materialism, attachment & detachment, God & the world, the Sant Mat teaches a lesson of ‘Practical Spirituality’ & ‘Better worldliness’ where religion is not only ethereal pursuit, but means for elevation of human consciousness for a positive disposition towards the entire creation of the Lord. There is a process of spiritual awakening that is happening in the world right now, which is still rather invisible to outer eyes, but which many are beginning to feel in their hearts. With the grace of supreme lord; the day is not far when this new spiritual consciousness will no longer be invisible, and the world as we know it will be transformed. Spiritual consciousness will not be separate from physical life, but an integral part of life. Spiritual consciousness will be shared among all living beings, and will be understood as the foundation upon which we build our lives on the Earth. This process has begun and is now catapulting us forward into one of the most significant times in the history of humanity.

REFERENCES

- Atam Gyan (Punjabi); Maharaj Jagat Singh Ji, Radhasoami Satsang, Beas (1984)
- Discourses on Education In Dayalbagh : A Vision of Complete Education; Radhasoami Satsang Sabha, Dayalbagh (2005)
- Discourses on Radhasoami Faith; Maharaj Sahib, Pt. Braham Shankar Mishra, Radhasoami Satsang Sabha, Dayalbagh (2004)
- Sant Mat Vichar (Punjabi); T.R. Shangari and K.S. Khaak, Radhasoami Satsang, Beas (1982)
- Sarbachan - Poetry (Hindi); Param Purush Pooran Dhani Huzur Soami Ji Maharaj, Radhasoami Satsang Sabha, Dayalbagh (2005)
- Writings and Speeches of Param Guru Huzur Sahabji Maharaj; Radhasoami Satsang Sabha, Dayalbagh (2006)